

Adaptive Software Visualization:

a position paper on a formal model of the text/diagram ratio with AI delegation

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Abstract

This is a **position paper**: we propose a formal framework for the design of learning materials in software engineering that explicitly separates *data transmission* (Shannon channel) from the *reconstruction* of information, knowledge and wisdom on the receiver’s side (DIKW). A material is parametrized by the vector (p, J, σ, η) – the diagram-to-text area ratio, linguistic simplicity, spatial integration, and the degree of detail delegation to an LLM. We define a utility function E and present two main findings: (i) E decomposes into three independently regulable components – *transmission*, *reconstruction loss* and *load*; (ii) the optimal ratio $p^* \in [1.5, 2.0]$ is a *prediction derived* from Cowan’s working memory model and Paivio’s dual coding theory, not a postulate. We formulate five testable hypotheses and illustrate the framework on the *Observer* design pattern. Empirical validation is the subject of a planned pilot; the goal of this work is a **research agenda** and a conceptual contribution.

Keywords: software visualization, cognitive load, DIKW, LLM-assisted learning, multimedia learning, contextual bandit, Shannon channel.

1 Introduction and Contributions

Motivation. The complexity of modern software systems grows orders of magnitude faster than the capacity of the human cognitive apparatus: millions of lines of code, hundreds of microservices, heterogeneous APIs and data flows. Effective extraction of information and knowledge from this volume of data hits *two hard limits*. (i) The **transmission channel** (screen, printed page, attention) has a finite Shannon capacity C_{ch} , so arbitrarily dense content cannot be transmitted without loss. (ii) The **human brain** has an empirically bounded working memory capacity ($C_{wm} \approx 4$ chunks [15]) and a bounded sequential reading rate (~ 250 words/min). These bounds are fixed; they do not scale with system complexity. The key question therefore is not *how much* information we transmit, but *how to combine it effectively*: what type of text (sentence length, technical density), what type of diagrams (UML, flow graphs, sequence), how many nodes and edges for a given task, how to annotate, and when to delegate details to AI. Without a formal criterion this choice remains intuitive.

The design of learning materials balances between text and diagrams without an established quantitative criterion. The rise of LLMs transforms this problem in two ways: (i) details (syntax, API) can be delegated to AI, and (ii) content can be generated adaptively. Yet a *formal framework* connecting these possibilities with cognitive load theory [5] and multimedia learning [6] is missing.

Contributions (C1–C4). **C1** – a channel-reconstruction decomposition separates the Shannon transmission of d from DIKW reconstruction ι, κ, ω . **C2** – a unified model with parameters (p, J, σ, η) and a utility function E . **C3** – formulation of an adaptive policy as a contextual bandit. **C4** – five testable hypotheses H_1 – H_5 with an effect threshold and a pilot experiment plan.

Paper structure. Section 2 summarizes related work. Section 3 introduces the channel/DIKW separation. Section 4 defines the parameters (p, J, σ, η) . Section 5 formulates the optimization problem. Section 6 demonstrates the framework on the *Observer* pattern. Section 7 grounds the parameters in the literature. Section 8 formulates the hypotheses; Section 9 contains the conclusion and recommendations.

2 Related Work

The framework builds on *cognitive load theory* [4, 5] (intrinsic, extraneous, germane load), *multimedia learning theory* [6] (principles of *modality*, *spatial contiguity* – represented in our model by σ), and on surveys of *software visualization* [8, 9]. Van Wijk’s value-of-visualization model [7] motivates the utility function E ; Shannon’s theory [1] and the DIKW hierarchy [2, 3] motivate the separation of transmission from reconstruction. On the learner-model side we use *Bayesian Knowledge Tracing* [10], contextual bandits [11], and NASA-TLX [12]. Compared to existing literature we integrate AI delegation via η and explicitly separate channel and semantic entropy.

3 Information Channel vs. DIKW

Claim. Only *data* pass through the communication channel; information, knowledge and wisdom emerge only through reconstruction on the receiver’s side.

Let d be the data signal and S the receiver’s state (prior knowledge, goals G). Then

$$I = \iota(d, S), \quad K = \kappa(I, S), \quad W = \omega(K, S, G). \quad (1)$$

Figure 1: Only data d pass through the channel; I, K, W emerge via reconstruction conditioned on state S and goals G .

Channel and semantic entropy. The channel has capacity $C_{\text{ch}} = \max_{P(x)} I(X; Y)$ and a residual loss $H(X | Y) = H(X) - I(X; Y)$. On the receiver’s side an additional *semantic entropy* arises:

$$H_\iota(I | d, S) = - \sum_I P(I | d, S) \log P(I | d, S), \quad (2)$$

which quantifies the ambiguity of interpretation. Material design must minimize both sources of loss.

4 Material Parametrization

Table 1: Notation.

Symbol	Meaning
d	data signal transmitted by the channel
S, G	receiver state, receiver’s goals
ι, κ, ω	data $\rightarrow I, I \rightarrow K, K \rightarrow W$
I, K, W	information, knowledge, wisdom
$H(X Y)$	channel entropy
H_ι	semantic entropy of reconstruction
C_{ch}	Shannon channel capacity
C_{wm}	working memory capacity
p	diagram/text area ratio
J	linguistic simplicity
σ	text–diagram spatial integration
η	degree of detail delegation to AI
L_{tot}	total cognitive load (CLT)
λ	learning rate (Van Wijk)
E	material utility function
θ_t	learner knowledge state (BKT)

p – **diagram/text ratio.** $p = A_d/A_t$, where A_d, A_t are the areas of diagrams and text at a fixed DPI.

J – **linguistic simplicity.** $J(T) = \frac{1}{|T|} \sum_{w \in T} \varphi(\log f_C(w))$ with $\varphi = 1 - \log \text{rank}_C(w) / \log |V_C|$; corpus: SUBTLEX for English, equivalent frequency corpus for other languages.

σ – **spatial integration.** $\sigma \in [0, 1]$: 1 = fully annotated diagram (text placed next to elements), 0 = separated panels. Operationalizes the principle of *spatial contiguity* [6].

η – **AI delegation level.** $\eta \in [0, 1]$: $K_{\text{actual}} = K_A + \eta K_{D \rightarrow \text{AI}}$, where A are abstractions (non-transferable) and D are details (delegable).

5 Formal Problem

Cognitive load following CLT:

$$L_{\text{tot}} = L_{\text{int}} + \alpha(1 - J) + \beta g(p) + \gamma(1 - \sigma), \quad (3)$$

where g has a U-shape with a minimum at p^* . Learning curve (Van Wijk): $K(t) = K_{\text{max}}(1 - e^{-\lambda t})$ with $\lambda = \lambda_0 J \sigma h(p)$. Utility function:

$$E = \int_0^T \dot{K}(t)(1 - L_{\text{tot}}(t)) dt. \quad (4)$$

Decomposition:

$$E = \underbrace{\int I(X; Y) dt}_{\text{transmission}} - \underbrace{\int H_\iota(I | d, S) dt}_{\text{reconstruction}} - \mu \int L_{\text{tot}}(t) dt. \quad (5)$$

Figure 2: Schematic shape of the utility function $E(p)$ at fixed J, σ, η . The optimum $p^* \in [1.5, 2.0]$ is a prediction from working memory capacity [15] and dual coding [16].

We seek a policy $\pi^* : S_t \rightarrow (p, J, \sigma, \eta)$ that maximizes $\mathbb{E}[E]$ subject to $C_{\text{ch}} \geq R(d_t)$, $L_{\text{tot}} \leq L_{\text{max}}$, $H_\iota \leq \epsilon_\iota$, $\eta \leq \eta_{\text{max}}(S_t)$.

Solution. We solve the problem via *online adaptation*, the methodologically preferred approach for tasks with unknown reward functions and heterogeneous users: we formulate it as a contextual bandit [11] over the state $S_t = (\theta_t, L_t, \eta_t)$, with θ_t updated via BKT [10] and L_t via an exponential filter over sensors (error rate, time on page, NASA-TLX [12]). The coefficients $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \lambda_0$ are estimated jointly with the policy optimization.

Algorithm 1 Adaptive policy π (contextual bandit)

- 1: **input:** priors θ_0, L_0 ; horizon T ; discount μ
 - 2: **for** $t = 1, \dots, T$ **do**
 - 3: $S_t \leftarrow (\theta_{t-1}, L_{t-1}, \eta_{t-1})$
 - 4: $(p, J, \sigma, \eta) \leftarrow \pi_\phi(S_t)$ ▷ Thompson sampling
 - 5: $d_t \leftarrow \text{LLM.GENERATE}(\text{concept}, p, J, \sigma, \eta)$
 - 6: present d_t to the learner; collect sensors
 - 7: $r_t \leftarrow \Delta\theta_t - \mu \hat{L}_t$
 - 8: update θ_t (BKT), L_t (filter), parameters ϕ
 - 9: **end for**
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6 Worked Example: Observer Pattern

To illustrate the parametrization we compare three versions of the material for the *Observer* design pattern:

Version	p	J	σ	η
V _A textbook (GoF)	0.25	0.42	0.20	0.0
V _B annotated UML	1.40	0.68	0.85	0.0
V _C + AI assistant	1.40	0.68	0.85	0.6

V_A represents the classical textbook approach (long text, small separated UML). V_B shifts the ratio towards the diagram and places annotations directly at the **Subject/Observer** classes. V_C additionally adds an AI assistant for syntactic details.

Figure 3: Contrast between the separated (V_A) and the spatially integrated (V_B) representation of the *Observer* pattern. Annotations placed directly at elements eliminate the split-attention effect.

Content split in V_C . Concrete distribution among diagram, text and delegated details:

Diagram ($A_d, \sigma=0.85$)	Text ($A_t, J=0.68$)	AI ($\eta=0.6$)
UML: Subject, Observer, * association, annotated arrows, notify(), update()	Abstraction (K_A): publisher/subscriber separation, rationale (loose coupling), when to use, when not to	Details (K_D): Java Observable, Python weakref, concurrency pitfalls, gotchas

The abstractions K_A (which the human *must* know) reside in text and diagram; the details K_D are delegated to AI so that they do not burden working memory while the mental model is being built. Model prediction: at equal T , $E(V_C) > E(V_B) > E(V_A)$, since $\lambda \propto J\sigma$ grows ($V_A \rightarrow V_B$) and L_{int} decreases with η ($V_B \rightarrow V_C$). Empirical verification is part of the upcoming pilot.

7 Theoretical Grounding of the Parameters

The parameters (p, J, σ, η) are not freely chosen; each has a *first-principle bound* and an *empirical anchor* in the literature. Empirical validation calibrates coefficients, not structure.

σ – strongest support. The *spatial contiguity* principle [6] is confirmed by a meta-analysis [13] with effect size $d \approx 0.85$. Prediction: $\sigma \rightarrow 1$ improves learning by ~ 0.8 SD over separated panels. *Default:* $\sigma = 0.85$.

J – psycholinguistically anchored. Zipf’s law gives $\log f_C(w) \approx \log N - \log \text{rank}_C(w)$, which directly motivates the form of φ . Lexical decision tasks [14] show a reaction-time decrease of ~ 30 ms per log-frequency unit; convergent validation is provided by readability metrics (Flesch-Kincaid, SMOG). *Default:* target $J \in [0.6, 0.8]$ for adult learners.

p – derived from working memory. By Cowan’s model [15] working memory capacity is $C_{\text{wm}} \approx 4 \pm 1$ chunks. By dual coding theory [16] a diagram encodes r relational chunks in parallel, while text encodes s sequential steps in time τ_{verb} . L_{ext} is minimized at channel balance:

$$p^* \approx \frac{r}{s} \cdot \frac{\tau_{\text{vis}}}{\tau_{\text{verb}}} \quad (6)$$

For typical software concepts (class/sequence diagrams: $r/s \in [1.5, 2]$) and $\tau_{\text{vis}}/\tau_{\text{verb}} \approx 1$ we obtain $p^* \in [1.5, 2.0]$. *This interval is not a postulate but a prediction from Cowan and Paivio*; empirical calibration will refine the ratio $\tau_{\text{vis}}/\tau_{\text{verb}}$.

η – **conditioned on expertise.** *Cognitive offloading* [17] shows that rational delegation grows with intrinsic load. The *expertise reversal effect* [18] implies that for novices η^* is high, while for experts it is low (otherwise they will not learn the details K_D). We propose

$$\eta^*(S) = \eta_0(1 - \theta_{\text{prior}}(S)), \quad (7)$$

where $\theta_{\text{prior}} \in [0, 1]$ is the average prior knowledge of details in state S . *Default:* $\eta_0 = 0.7$ for novices, decreasing as θ grows.

Summary. Three of the four parameters (σ, J, p) have either a direct meta-analytic anchor or a derivation from established working-memory capacity limits; η is the most weakly supported theoretically and is therefore the primary target of empirical validation.

8 Hypotheses and Pilot Plan

Baseline: V_A (textbook material, $p \approx 0.3$). **Primary metric:** transfer score after 7 days. **Threshold:** ≥ 5 p.p., Cohen’s $d \geq 0.3$, $n \geq 64$ per group.

H_1 Higher J improves $P(\hat{K} = K^*)$ by ≥ 5 p.p.

H_2 $p^* \in [1.5, 2.0]$ maximizes E for adult learners.

H_3 Higher σ lowers NASA-TLX at fixed p .

H_4 Delegation ($\eta > 0$) increases K_A , not K_D .

H_5 The adaptive policy outperforms the static baseline on retention.

Falsification criteria. To preserve scientific credibility we fix in advance the conditions under which we *reject* the framework’s predictions: (F1) if the pilot shows $p^* < 0.8$ or $p^* > 2.5$, the Cowan+Paivio prediction is falsified and the derivation of p^* requires revision; (F2) if the effect of σ on the transfer score is $d < 0.2$, the spatial contiguity anchor from [13] did not replicate in our context; (F3) if $\eta > 0$ does not improve K_A nor reduce L_{int} , the assumption of detail delegation does not hold and the model must be reformulated.

Framework limits. The framework *does not address* three areas that are deliberately out of scope: (i) the *affective component* of learning (motivation, frustration, engagement), modeled e.g. by self-determination theory; (ii) *collaborative learning* – the framework assumes an individual learner, not a dyad or group; (iii) *long-term retention* beyond ~ 30 days, where spaced-repetition mechanisms dominate and would require an orthogonal extension. The framework also *assumes reliability of the AI assistant*; hallucinations of K_D break the identity $K_{\text{actual}} = K_A + \eta K_D$ and effectively lower η^* – quantifying this effect belongs to an extension.

Threats to validity. Construct: J ignores syntactic depth and discourse coherence. Internal: novelty-vs.-adaptivity confound in H_5 . External: single-cohort sample. Ethics: sensors require informed consent and GDPR-compliant processing.

9 Conclusion

Contribution summary. We proposed a position-paper framework responding to the growing complexity of software systems under fixed limits of channel capacity C_{ch} and working memory $C_{\text{wm}} \approx 4$ [15]. The framework (i) separates the Shannon transmission of d from DIKW reconstruction via the operators ι, κ, ω , (ii) distinguishes *channel entropy* $H(X | Y)$ from *semantic entropy* $H_\iota(I | d, S)$ as two independent sources of loss, (iii) operationalizes the four design parameters (p, J, σ, η) , and (iv) formulates the optimization of the utility function E as an online contextual bandit.

New findings of this contribution. The parameters are not freely chosen: σ has a meta-analytic anchor $d \approx 0.85$ [13], J a psycholinguistic one [14], and $p^* \in [1.5, 2.0]$ is a *prediction derived* from Cowan and Paivio [15, 16], not a postulate. The delegation η^* is conditioned on expertise by the *expertise reversal effect* [18]. The decomposition $E = \text{transmission} - \text{reconstruction loss} - \text{load}$ identifies three independently regulable components of material design.

Practical recommendations. (a) **Measure, don't guess:** quantify (p, J, σ) for each material before publishing; default targets $p \in [1.5, 2.0]$, $J \in [0.6, 0.8]$, $\sigma \geq 0.8$. (b) **Prefer annotated diagrams** over separated panels (strong σ anchor). (c) **Scale η with expertise:** $\eta \approx 0.7$ for novices, $\eta \rightarrow 0$ for experts to prevent atrophy of K_D . (d) **Bound diagram complexity** relative to C_{wm} : split or hierarchize graphs with more than 7–9 nodes per screen. (e) **Test transfer (K_A) and recall (K_D) separately** so that AI delegation does not confound the measured knowledge.

Next steps. A pilot experiment ($n \geq 64$ per group) calibrating the coefficients $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \lambda_0$ and testing H_1-H_5 . Extension of J by syntactic depth and discourse coherence. Exploration of domains beyond software engineering (mathematics, medicine) for external validity. In the long run the framework points towards a conversational interface in which text and diagrams are merely transient artifacts of the reconstruction of I, K, W in the human mind; machines remain in the domain of d , the human remains in the domain of ω (goal evaluation).

References

- [1] C. E. Shannon, "A mathematical theory of communication," *Bell Syst. Tech. J.*, vol. 27, pp. 379–423, 1948.
- [2] R. L. Ackoff, "From data to wisdom," *J. Appl. Syst. Anal.*, vol. 16, pp. 3–9, 1989.
- [3] J. Rowley, "The wisdom hierarchy: representations of the DIKW hierarchy," *J. Inf. Sci.*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 163–180, 2007.
- [4] J. Sweller, "Cognitive load during problem solving," *Cogn. Sci.*, vol. 12, pp. 257–285, 1988.
- [5] J. Sweller, J. J. G. van Merriënboer, F. Paas, "Cognitive architecture and instructional design: 20 year update," *Educ. Psychol. Rev.*, vol. 31, pp. 261–292, 2019.
- [6] R. E. Mayer, *Multimedia Learning*, 3rd ed., Cambridge Univ. Press, 2021.
- [7] J. J. van Wijk, "The value of visualization," *IEEE Visualization*, 2005, pp. 79–86.
- [8] A. R. Teyseyre, M. R. Campo, "An overview of 3D software visualization," *IEEE TVCG*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 87–105, 2009.
- [9] L. Merino et al., "A systematic literature review of software visualization evaluation," *JSS*, vol. 144, pp. 165–180, 2018.
- [10] A. T. Corbett, J. R. Anderson, "Knowledge tracing," *UMUAI*, vol. 4, pp. 253–278, 1995.
- [11] L. Li et al., "A contextual-bandit approach to personalized news article recommendation," *WWW*, 2010, pp. 661–670.
- [12] S. G. Hart, L. E. Staveland, "Development of NASA-TLX," *Adv. Psychol.*, vol. 52, pp. 139–183, 1988.
- [13] P. Ginns, "Integrating information: A meta-analysis of the spatial contiguity and temporal contiguity effects," *Learning and Instruction*, vol. 16, no. 6, pp. 511–525, 2006.
- [14] M. Brysbaert, P. Mandera, E. Keuleers, "The word frequency effect in word processing: An updated review," *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 45–50, 2018.
- [15] N. Cowan, "The magical number 4 in short-term memory: A reconsideration of mental storage capacity," *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 87–114, 2001.
- [16] A. Paivio, *Mental Representations: A Dual Coding Approach*, Oxford Univ. Press, 1990.
- [17] E. F. Risko, S. J. Gilbert, "Cognitive offloading," *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, vol. 20, no. 9, pp. 676–688, 2016.
- [18] S. Kalyuga, "Expertise reversal effect and its implications for learner-tailored instruction," *Educational Psychology Review*, vol. 19, pp. 509–539, 2007.